

The Impact of Demographic Profile on Strategic HRM Practices and Its Challenges Faced by HR Managers in IT Firm, India: An Empirical Study

P. Saravanan, A. Vasumathi

Abstract—The authors conducted a study for the sample size of 75 HR managers from an Indian IT company through systematic sampling method. This study identifies that the female employees are facing lesser conflict than the male employees against their managers within the organization. There is a positive correlation between gender and conflict management with the superior towards the work. There is a significant variance between age and response towards appraisal system, succession planning and employee engagement. The education qualification plays a major role in determining the compensation factor for the employees working in the organization. The study determines the impact of demographic profile on strategic HRM practices and its challenges faced by HR managers in IT firm, India.

Keywords—Strategic Human resource management, Change agent, Employee engagement, Performance management, Succession planning and Conflict management.

I. INTRODUCTION

DURING 1920s the importance of personal management functions were recognized in India. As per Royal commission report in 1931, the welfare officers were employed to handle their employees and address the grievances towards the work. As per Factories act 1948, appointment of welfare officers are mandatory if the company is employed with more than 500 employees within the organization. Two professional institutes named “Indian institute of personnel management” in Calcutta and “National institute of labour management” in Bombay were formed by the government to promote the personnel management, industrial relations, welfare and administrative functions and their activities during 1960s in India. During 1970’s the focus shifted from welfare activities to increase the productivity of the employees. In 1980’s the HRM functions were emerged and the focus shifted from administrative activities to modern business HR functions [1]. HRM functions plays a vital roles in modern organizations especially in current scenario, since there is a shift in personnel management functions such as employee record maintenance, administrative functions in to strategic HR functions like partnering with business, building high performance team, creating better work climate, hassle-free work environment within the organisation. Human resource functions helps in motivating the employees to

increase the performance towards the work in order to achieve the goals and objectives for the company which leads to gain the competitive advantage in the change in business environment and its functions. Effective implementation and utilization of HRM functions and its practices towards the volatile business functions will lead to win-over the competitive strategies and obtain the objectives for the organisation [4].

Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) plays a vital role in formulating the policies and strategies for the company, in order to fulfill the employee’s requirement and to perform the job efficiently within the organization. Human Resource Management (HRM) functions helps in attracting and motivating the talented workforce for the organization and by increasing the performance of an individual, will result in achieving the defined goals and objectives for the company [77].

HR managers acts an important role in the organisation by incorporating the strategic HRM practices that helps in increasing the satisfaction level of workers and increasing the sustainability factor for the business functions within the industry [10]. HR managers plays a wider role in the organisation such as change agent, business enabler, administrative expert which helps in driving the business functions successfully and overcome the challenges faced by the organisation [13].

HRM function plays an important role in managing the workers within organisation through a formal communication channel. Since HR functions acts as a mediatory role in between the employee as well as the employers within the organisation that helps in improving the efficacy and skills of the individuals employed within the company. HR manager acts as a change agent, enabling and driving the change management program with respect to business HR functions and its future requirements of the company. Due to change in the business environment, the focus of HR manager is shifting from administrative/personnal functions in to a strategic business HR function. HR managers plays a strategic role in managing various HR functions such as recruitment and selection, human resource information system, manpower planning, performance management, conflict management, employee engagement, compensation management, policy formation and retention strategies followed within the industry [78].

Major challenges faced by HR managers at work place are managing the level of engagement for the talented resources

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within the organisation, reducing the conflicts at workplace, mapping the talented resources through succession planning process, building the effective appraisal process and performance management system and mapping the compensation based on the skills and experience possessed by the employee within the company [79].

HRM plays a significant role in promoting and maximizing the efficacy of the employee, in the present scenario the role of HR managers are changing due to rapid change in the technologies, demand from trade unions, change in the government policies and procedures. Hence revamping the human resource functions through effective HR planning and its strategies, increasing the motivation levels of employees at work, effective recruitment process, creating a better learning environment and organizing best employee engagement activities at work which helps in retaining the best talented resources within the organization [2].

II. IT INDUSTRY IN INDIA

As per National association of software and services companies report, the IT industry achieved \$118 billion in FY 2014 and expected revenue for FY 2015 is \$130 Billion, the industry has grown up to 13 % in FY 2014 and expected to grow up to 13 -15 % in FY 2015 and the domestic market is expected to grow around 9-12 % in FY 2015. The industry has close to 16,000 firms and 6-8% of new customer additions through alliances, partnering and collaborating with existing clients. The IT industry contributes 10-12 % of the GDP in FY 15. IT industry has spread across in to major four verticals such as manufacturing, retail, health care, government, and Banking & Financial service industry. The industry also targets to invest on developing sectors like telecom, e-commerce, cloud, hospitality, energy and utility, transportation and entertainment & media services etc. [19]

IT industry plays a significant role in driving India's growth and its economic development. IT sector is considered to be one of the fast growing industry when compared to other industries in the market which promotes the growth and economic development of the country. This industry generates huge job opportunities and employs millions of employees directly and indirectly through various sectors such as construction, telecom and communication, power sector, transport etc. Indian IT organisations offer wide range of services that enables the consumers with high quality products and services at low cost. These companies gains the technical advancements through merger, acquisitions, alliancing and partnering with foreign companies that helps in offering wide range of new service offerings to the end user in the market. The major revenue generates through the following tier-1 cities like Mumbai, Bangalore, Hyderabad and Chennai and the operations are expanded to Tier –ii cities such as Chandigarh, Gurgaon, Trivandrum, Bhubaneswar, Noida and Pune [18].

Indian IT organisations generate huge job opportunities in the market. More multinational companies enticed to Indian IT organisations due to wide range of service offering and quality of products and service offered to the end users. Around 60%

of the Indian IT industry revenue is generated through US companies and 40 % of revenue is generated through European and middle- east countries etc. Indian organisations are valued for their quality of services, deliverables on time, flexibility towards the work and gaining technological advancements through partnering and collaborating with global players in the market [17].

India is considered as one of the world's largest attractive destination for IT companies, considering availability of huge manpower, infrastructure, implementation of international delivery model etc. Indian IT industries expands their operations to other part of the work like European countries, Latin America and South East-Asian countries in order to attract the local customers and gain the competitive advantage in the industry [20].

III. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Conflict among the workers will lead to a negative impression on the company, which needs to be resolved immediately. This could create disputes within the employees at the organization [35]. Female employees are able to manage the conflicts through ignoring politely, avoiding the conflict rather than male employees in terms of managing the conflicts among peers [68].

HR managers should increase their not only towards the salary, they need to build the relationship between their salary and their performance outcomes towards the job. This program will create a positive impact towards the business results and improve the efficiency of the organization [69].

HR plays a significant role in engaging their employees, since engaged employee will have positive attitude, focus towards the work, which result in building the high performance workforce within the organisation [70]. Engaged workforce will contributes to business results, generates revenue for the company and helps in gaining the competitive advantage with in the industry [7].

HR managers should focus on maximizing and utilizing the resources available internally through succession planning process. Since this process helps to identify the potential resources and future leaders available within the company for key management profiles. This tool acts as career advancements for the employees to move up the ladder and take up the challenging roles available within the organization [71]. HR managers focus on bridging the gap between present and future requirements of the company through succession planning initiative organized by the company, which result in younger age group contributes to higher level of companies' performance than the middle or older age group of respondent within the organization [72].

HR managers evaluates and appraises the performance of an employee through performance appraisal process, this process helps in identifying the key strength and weakness of an employee based on the past performance and overcome the future challenges faced by the organization which result in increase in the efficacy of the individual, increase in pay and incentive based on the performance of an employee towards the work [73]. Through continues improvement process and

feedback from the managers, the focus towards customer's requirements are increased, which result in offering wide range of service offerings to customers in order to gain competitive advantage within the industry [74].

Compensation management determines the wage levels of the employees based on the education and experience carried by the individual which has a direct impact on the organizational performance and its business outcomes [76].

By reviewing various literatures, the researchers identified the IT industry employer's attitude and work culture, behavior, conflict management with managers, succession planning process, performance management, employee engagement programs, appraisal systems, compensation management, learning opportunities and work environments are completely different from other industries. The HR managers in IT firm's faces issues related to performance aspects, increasing the engagement levels for the employees at work, identifying the resources internally, managing the stress at work, avoiding conflicts with the managers and peers. The conflict management that leads to unhealthy work culture among employees and employers which leads to raise in the attrition levels for the organization. By reading various literatures, no one studied the impact of demographic profile on strategic HRM practices and its challenges faced by HR managers in IT firm. This motivates the researchers to conduct the study on the same.

IV. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objective of the study is

- To identify the impact of demographic profile on strategic HRM practices and its challenges faced by HR managers in IT firm, India.
- To find the relationship between gender and their response to conflict management with supervisor at work.
- To find out the association between annual income and their response towards performance management followed by the company.
- To find the significant variance between age and their response towards the employee engagement, succession planning and appraisal process followed by the company.
- To find out the impact of demographic profile of the respondents towards compensation management that matches the skills and experience offered by the company.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Strategic HRM Practices

SHRM practices play a crucial role in encouraging and motivating the employees in order to express the positive approaches, skills and behaviors which required to support and incorporate the necessary strategy for the company to gain competitive advantage [5]. Most of the companies treats HRM practices as the corporate strategies that motivates and enhance the work culture, building relationship with consumers, strengthen and encourages the workforce through participative management within the organisation [6].

SHRM practices are realigned towards the organisation strategies that contribute and promote technology advancements, innovative skills and knowledge delivered by an individual within the company [8]. These practices also make sure that the company utilizes the full potentials of an individual and the necessary skills to obtain the goals and objective for the company [9]. Strategic HRM primary focus on aligning the HRM practices in line with the organization strategies, the assimilation of human resource management in the organization strategies through participation and involvement of top management teams towards strategic approach which is related to recruitment and selection process, compensation reviews, performance management that adds value and has a direct impact on company performance through HRM practices and its strategies [3].

HRM practices and its strategies acts as a building block which result in developing the specific competencies, skills, attitude and knowledge of an employees in the organisation to gain competitive advantage within the industry [12]. HRM practices acts as a retentions tool which generates the positive relationship between employee and employer in the organisation and these practices offers job security, competency and skill based training opportunities, effective communication and retention strategies which motivates the employees to stay with the organisation [11].

B. HR Planning and Succession Planning

HR planning is a systematic process of analyzing and forecasting the future demands and supply of workers in order to deploy the required skills and attitude to obtain the objectives of the company. HR planning guides the company by predicting the changes in the strategy and the impact factor on the needs and requirements of HR. Planning acts a important tool in predicting the needs of the employee and with respect to change in the demand from external markets [14]. HR planning generates positive relationship which has a direct impact on employee's productivity [15]. HR planning acts as an important tool for HR managers to ensure the company has right no of resources available at right place, at right time with right set of skills in order to accomplish the job effectively which is required by the employer within the organization [58] The HR planning is a tool that helps in obtaining the strategic objective and goals for the company [59].

Succession planning is process of identifying and selecting the employee within the organisation based on their competencies, skills and attitudes, personality, behavior, extraordinary performance, highly motivated towards the work and positive approach towards the organisation [16] preparing them for attaining the new role within the organisation [27]. HR manager's plays a crucial role in matching the future engagement/ requirements through resources available internally based on their capability and skills expressed during the current engagements within the organisation [25]. This process helps in identifying the individuals internally within the organisation who will be eligible to take up the future /

emerging opportunities in the company over a period of time [26].

C. HR Business Leader

HR leaders play an important role in decision making process that determines the success factor for the organisation [21]. HR leaders should incorporate the necessary policies and strategies which add value to the organisation and increase the efficiency of the employees through various initiatives like introducing new technologies, job rotations, consulting support, promoting automation, motivating and engaging the talented work force within the organisation [22].

HR business leaders should focus on the current trends and the future challenges in which the business function operates. HR should consider the other parties like consumers, shareholders, communities and other stake holders will framing the policies and strategies for the company. HR leaders need to convert the investments from training initiatives, talent branding, talent engagements and performance improvements in to a future business results and its outcome for the company [23], [24].

D. HR Role on Generating the Workers' Participation

HR acts as a mediatory role between employee and employer, through negotiating and identifying the solution for the conflict by creating the participative management in decision making process, generating the mutual trust among the workers and management [28]. Employee's involvement in decision making process play a significant role in increasing companies performance and its business function [29]. Employers should increase the participation employees through sharing information related to future plans and prospects of the company, creating the common platform for communication that reduces the gap between employee and employer which motives to achieve the goals and objectives for the company [30].

HR plays an important role in bridging the gap between the workers and management through participative management, offering wide range of training opportunities to increase the performance of the employee and firm's performance [31]. The success factor of employee participation is through involvement and encouragement by top management officials and HR managers, which helps in creating the friendly work culture and environment leads to better relationship among the employee and employer within the organization [32], [33].

E. HR as a Strategic Partner Role

HR managers should act as a strategic partner, through involving top management professionals in to strategic decisions process by aligning the HR policies and strategies with business objective and its functions. HRM policies and practices plays important role in influencing the business strategies and its outcomes within the organization [42].

HR should partner with line manager by offering wide range of training opportunities, creating effective communication channel, reward and recognition schemes in line with the HR policies and practices offered by the company [43]. HR manager formulates the innovative policies

and strategies with reference to the business function and its future requirements of the organisation [44]. HR manager should identify the changing needs of business, resist to change, more adaptive to the business situations, customer focused etc. HR functions plays a strategic role in managing and operating the business function through various initiatives such as succession planning process, career development, better compensation system and retention strategies for the workers within the organisation. Since employee's acts as a backbone for the company, the employers will be able to obtain the objective of the company only with the support of the worker within the organization [45].

F. HR Role in Building the High Performance Workforce

HR managers should create an effective performance management system with the help of line manager and the top management professionals that will help in increasing the productivity level and performance of an employee towards the work. HR should generate the necessary competencies to ensure that appropriate tools were used to monitor the performance of an employee within the organisation [37]. Effective performance management system will lead to generate the high performance work force through defining the individual goals and objectives, performance evaluation and improvements tracking through a common system will ensure the performance of the employee is in line with the goals and objective of the company [38], [49].

Performance management is a continuous process that helps in identify, measure and develop the performance of an employee, team and mapping their outcome with the organisation goals and its objectives. It guides the individual, group of employee and enables them to identify and develop their knowledge through mentoring, training initiatives which result in achieving the goals and objectives for the company [46]. HR managers use the performance management system as a strategic tool for measuring the performance of an individual in the company. Monitoring the performance of individuals and organization goals, will result in developing the required competency for the job that helps in better understanding on the defined and future goals for the company [47], [48].

G. HR Role in Engaging the Work Force

HR plays an important role in engaging the employee, since employee are the assets for the company. This engagement process acts as a critical success factor for the business function, where the HR plays a strategic role in formulating the necessary policies and strategies for generating and increasing the commitment level of an individual's towards the work [49]. The employee engagement has a direct impact on the organisation performance and helps in increase productivity level of an employee within the organisation. Employee engagement process acts as a one of the best retention tool that helps in retaining the employees in the organisation which result in generating the higher level of consumer satisfaction, increase in stakeholder value and builds

companies image and reputation in the industry [50]-[54] and [56].

HR manager plays a significant role in engaging the employees within the organisation. If the HR has not addressed the issues with clear approach and the employees fail to engage which leads to mismanage the function or the job roles within the organization [55]. Engaged workforce will have a direct impact on increasing the job performance at work, express the positive outcomes at work place, self-motivated, builds better work culture and compete themselves to perform the job effectively within the organisation [57].

H.HR as a Change Enabler

HR manager acts as a change agent and drives the change management initiatives in the organisation and ensure the balance with the employee and employers with respect to the change process within the organisation [34]. This change process ideally increases the company performance in terms of increase in productivity and its operations without any overhead cost. The change management with in the company

will have a direct impact on the potential employees within the organisation. Hence human resource managers should create a project plan which result in increasing the performance of the organisation and creates the better work environment for the employee within the company [35]. HR professionals implement the change process by appropriate communication plan, aligning the various projects which respect to the business function that enables the change in order to overcome the challenges faced by the organisations [36]. The change process has a direct impact on internal or external functions like individuals are a group of employees for initiate, direct, implement and manage the change initiative projects and its functions [40]. HR managers guides and improve the work flow with the help of line manager and execute the change process within the company [39]. HR as a change agent brings the successful transformation within the organisation and significant change in the work culture will result in increase in performance of any individual and obtain the objectives of the company [41].

Fig. 1 Theoretical model on modern HR functions

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Type of research

The purpose of using the descriptive research is to study the phenomenon on which occurs at specific time and place. Basis on the said factor, descriptive type of research is implemented in the study.

B. Sample

The sample size defined as:

$$n = (z\sigma / d)^2$$

where n- Sample size of the population. z = Value at a complete level of confidence. σ = Standard deviation of the population. d = Difference between the sample mean and population mean.

It is difficult to classify the standard deviation and population mean, hence the researchers used systematic

sampling method and the conducted a survey with HR managers from an IT firm in India. This IT company has its operations spread across 10 development centers in India, the company's headquarters located in Bangalore and operates from various locations such as Mangalore, Mysore, Chennai, Trivandrum, Pune, Chandigarh, Bhubaneshwar, Hyderabad and Jaipur with around 450 HR managers were employed through various branches of this IT firm in India. In Bangalore development center, around 150 HR managers were employed in this IT firm. Hence the researchers approached 75 respondents, who are willing to respond for the primary data collection through questionnaire was considered as sample size for this study. This is the main limitation of the study.

C. Research Instrument

This study is purely empirical in nature, hence questionnaire were used as an instrument for data collections for the study. The researchers have framed a well-structured

questionnaire that consists of three categories. The first category deals with the demographic profile of the HR manager, the second category focuses on the questions related to the strategic HRM practices and its issues the third category consists of challenges faced by HR managers in IT firm. The researchers has done a validity test for the variables in the questionnaire in order to measure the strategic HRM practices, issues and challenges handled by HR manager (19 items with Likert scale in the questionnaire) and obtained $\alpha=0.7$. The questions were used for the validity test such as response towards their "Conflict management", their response about "Performance management", "Employee engagement activities", "Succession planning", "Appraisal system" and "Compensation management" etc.

D. Sources of Data

Primary source of data collected through questionnaires and the secondary source of data's are collected through articles, business journals, magazines, publications and hand book of IT firm.

E. Data Analysis Procedures

The primary data collected through questionnaires and their responses were entered and analyzed by using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) for analysis. Pearson's Chi-Square test used to identify whether two random variables are independent in nature. Hence, the researchers were finding out the level of association between the annual income and their response towards the performance management within the organisation. Correlation analysis used to identify the degree of relationship between dependent and independent variable. Hence, the researchers were finding out the relationship between gender and their response towards the conflict management with supervisor at work. ANOVA is used to identify the significant variance between one independent variable and many dependent variables. Therefore, the researchers were finding out the variance between age and response towards the appraisal system, succession planning and employee engagement initiative offered by the company. Discriminant analysis is used to identify the association between one dependent variable (dichotomous questionnaire) and many independent variables. Hence, discriminant analysis used to find out the significant association between the career development initiative with gender, age, annual income, educational qualification and compensation management offered by the company.

VII. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

A. Correlation Analysis

Identify the relationship between gender and their response towards the conflict management with the supervisor at work.

The Pearson's R correlation value (see Table II) is 0.115. Which reveals that there is a positive correlation between gender and the conflict management with supervisor at work. Most of the male respondents were facing higher level of conflict with supervisor when compared to female respondents

towards the work.

TABLE I
CONFLICT MANAGEMENT

Gender	Conflict					Total
	Always	Some times	often	Rarely	Never	
Male	3	8	6	11	6	34
Female	1	9	6	17	8	41
Total	4	17	12	28	14	75

TABLE II
CORRELATION VALUE

	Value	Asymp. Std. Error	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Interval by Interval Pearson's R	.115	.115	.988	.327
Ordinal by Ordinal Spearman Correlation	.105	.115	.906	.368
N of valid cases	75			

B. Chi-Square Test

H1. There is a significant association between annual income and their response towards performance management followed by the company.

TABLE III
PEARSON CHI-SQUARE VALUE

Particulars	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.801	12	.633
Likelihood Ratio	10.874	12	.540
Linear-by-Linear Association	.434	1	.510
N of Valid Cases	75		

TABLE IV
SYMMETRIC MEASURES

Particulars	Value	Approx.sig
Nominal by Nominal Phi	.361	.633
Cramer's V	.209	.633
N of Valid cases	75	

TABLE V
DIRECTIONAL MEASURES

Particulars	Value	Asym. Std.Err	Approx. T	Approx. Sig.
Nominal By Nominal Lambda	Symmetric .057 Performance .000	.029 .000	1.936	.053
Goodman and Kruskal tau	Mgt Annual income .096 Performance .027 Mgt Annual income .047	.048 .022 .020	1.936	.053 .783 .573

The Pearson Chi-square value (see Table III) is 0.633. The significance level calculated at 95 percent of confidence level out of 100 percent, which is greater than the hypothetical value of 0.05. Hence H1 is accepted and there is a significant association between annual income and their response towards performance management followed by the company. The Cramer's V 0.633 (see Table IV) reveals that there is a moderate association between annual income and their response towards performance management followed by the company. The asymmetric lambda value 0.000 (see Table V) infers that there is a 0% error reduction in predicting the response towards the performance management when the annual income of respondents is known. If the lambda value

increases then the dependent variable could be predicted more accurately. Hence the researchers could not predict more precisely the responses towards performance management when the annual income of the respondent was known.

C. Analysis of Variance

- H2. There is a significant variance between age and their response towards employee engagement program organized within the company.
- H3. There is a significant variance between age and their response towards succession planning program organized within the company.
- H4. There is a significant variance between age and their response towards appraisal system followed within the company.

TABLE VI
DESCRIPTIVES

	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std. Err	95% Confidence interval for Mean		Min	Max
					Low	Up		
Emp Eng								
18-25 Yrs	20	2.30	.865	.193	1.90	2.70	1	4
26-30 Yrs	39	2.13	.801	.128	1.87	2.39	1	4
31-35 Yrs	12	2.00	.603	.174	1.62	2.38	1	3
36-40 Yrs	4	1.50	.577	.289	.58	2.42	1	2
Total	75	2.12	.788	.091	1.94	2.30	1	4
Suc Plan								
18-25 Yrs	20	2.40	.598	.134	2.12	2.68	1	3
26-30 Yrs	39	2.28	.759	.122	2.04	2.53	1	4
31-35 Yrs	12	2.08	.669	.193	1.66	2.51	1	3
36-40 Yrs	4	2.25	.500	.250	1.45	3.05	2	3
Total	75	2.28	.689	.080	2.12	2.44	1	4
Appraisal								
18-25 Yrs	20	2.35	1.089	.244	1.84	2.86	1	5
26-30 Yrs	39	2.44	1.119	.179	2.07	2.80	1	5
31-35 Yrs	12	2.08	.996	.288	1.45	2.72	1	4
36-40 Yrs	4	2.25	1.258	.629	.25	4.25	1	4
Total	75	2.35	1.084	.125	2.10	2.60	1	5

From Table VI, the first item's highest mean score is 1.25, which infers that the HR managers with the age group of 18-25 years responded that more employee engagement initiatives were organized by the company and the least mean score is 1.50, it infers that respondents' age group of 36-40 years responded that lesser employee engagement initiatives were organized within the company. The second items highest mean score is 2.40, it proves that age group of 18-25 years were responded that the succession planning programs organized by the company was more effective and the least mean score is 2.08, it infers that respondents age group of 31-35 years responded that the succession planning program organized by the company was less effective. The third items highest mean score is 2.44, it proves the respondents age group of 26-30 years responded that appraisal system followed by company is more effective and the least mean score is 2.08, it infers that respondents' age group of 31-35 years responded that appraisal system followed by the company is less effective. The mean scores (see Table VI), it proves that the respondents' age group of 36-40 years was less motivated to employee engagement initiatives organized within the company. The respondent age group of 31-35 years was less

motivated to succession planning and appraisal system followed within the company.

TABLE VII
ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Emp Eng					
Between Groups	2.361	3	.787	1.283	.287
Within Groups	43.559	71	.614		
Total	45.920	74			
Suc Plan					
Between Groups	.756	3	.252	.521	.669
Within Groups	34.364	71	.484		
Total	35.120	74			
Appraisal					
Between Groups	1.180	3	.393	.326	.807
Within Groups	85.806	71	1.209		
Total	86.987	74			

The significance value of Employee engagement, succession planning and Appraisal system is respectively as 0.287, 0.669 and 0.809 (see Table VII), which is greater than the p value 0.05 and hence H2, H3, and H4 are accepted. The same results were obtained the corresponding F values. Hence, there is a significant age groups and their response towards employee engagement, succession planning and appraisal system. The study also proves that the employees' age group of 18-25 years was highly motivated through employee engagement, succession planning and effective appraisal system in the IT industry which helps in attract and retain the best talents within the industry, considering majority individuals falling under this age category. Respondents age group between 31-35 years are less motivated to employee engagement, succession planning programs and appraisal system due to lesser number of individuals falling under this age group.

D. Discriminant Analysis

There is a significant association between the gender, age, education qualification, annual income and years of experience with compensation that matches the skills and experience offered by the company.

TABLE VIII
WILKS' LAMBDA

Test of Fun(s)	Wilks' Lamda	Chi-Square	DF	Sig
1	0.910	6.685	5	.245

TABLE IX
STANDARDIZED CANONICAL DISCRIMINANT FUNCTION COEFFICIENTS

Particulars	Function
	1
Gender	0.057
Age	0.723
Education Qualification	0.787
Annual Income	-0.937
Yrs of Exp	-0.001

The classification matrix (see Table X) indicates that the discriminant function is able to classify 60 Percent of 75 objects correctly. The wilks' lambda value (see Table VIII) is

0.910. It is between 0 and 1 and indicates better discriminating power of the selected variables. The probability value of the F test indicates that the discrimination between the two groups is highly significant. This is because $P < 0.107$, which indicates that the F test would be significant at a confidence level up to $(1 - 0.245) \times 100$ or 75.5 percent. Hence accept H_5 .

TABLE X
CANONICAL DISCRIMINANT FUNCTION COEFFICIENTS

Particulars	Function
	1
Gender	0.114
Age	0.905
Education Qualification	1.227
Annual Income	-0.845
Yrs of Exp	-0.002
(Constant)	-2.961

Unstandardized coefficients

TABLE XI
FUNCTIONS AT GROUP CENTROIDS

Career Development	Function
	1
No	-0.427
Yes	0.227

Unstandardized canonical discriminant functions evaluated at group means

TABLE XII
CLASSIFICATION RESULTS

Details	Grievances	Predicted Group Membership		Total
		Yes	No	
Original	Count	28	21	49
	%	57.1	42.9	100.0
60 % of original grouped cases correctly classified.	Count	9	17	26
	%	34.6	65.4	100.0

The standardized coefficient in the output (see Table IX), reveals that the education qualification is the best predictor, with the coefficient of 0.787, followed by age with the coefficient of 0.723, gender with the coefficient of 0.057, annual income with the coefficient of -0.937 and years of experience with the coefficient of -0.001.

The means of the canonical variables in (see Table XI) gives the new means for the transformed group centroids. Thus, the new mean for group 1 (Compensation not matching the skills and Experience) is -0.427 and the new mean for group 2 (Compensation matching skills and experience) is 0.227. This means that the midpoint of these two is 0. The projections will be clear when the two means are plotted in the straight line and by locating their mid points, as shown below (See Fig. 2).

If the discriminant score of a respondent falls to the left of the mid points which inters that the respondent rated that the compensation matching the skills and experience offered by the company, if the score of the respondent falls to the right of the midpoint, the respondent could determine that the compensation is not matching the skills and experience offered by the company. Therefore any positive (greater than

0) value of the discriminant score will lead to classification as 'compensation matching the skills and experience offered by the company' and any negative (less than 0) value of the discriminant score will lead to classification as 'compensation is not matching the skills and experience offered by the company'.

Fig. 2 Discriminant scale

Unstandardized discriminant function from (See Table X), is

$$Y = -2.961 + 0.114 (\text{gender}) + 0.905 (\text{age}) + 1.227 (\text{education qualification}) - 0.845 (\text{Annual income}) - 0.002 (\text{yrs of exp}).$$

Y gives the discriminant score of any person based on their gender, age, education qualification, annual income and years of experience categories.

For example a female HR manager with age group of 26-35 yrs, completed her post-graduation and currently holding an experience of greater than 12 yrs of experience falls under the annual income of greater than 7 lakhs provided that the compensation matches the skills and experience offered by the company. This can be proved in the following equation

The researches had coded in SPSS as follows: A female HR manager respondent (coded in SPSS is 2), falls under age group of 26-35 years (2), education qualification as post-graduation (3), annual income greater than 7 lakhs (4), with greater than 12 yrs of experience (4). By calculating the value with above said discriminant function, the discriminant score Y is

$$Y = -2.961 + 0.114 (2) + 0.905 (4) + 1.227 (3) - 0.845 (4) - 0.002 (4).$$

$$Y = -2.961 + 0.228 + 3.62 + 3.681 - 3.38 - 0.008$$

$$Y = 1.18$$

VIII. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

Basis on the research and outcome of the survey from HR managers, it is identified that the majority of the male respondents were facing higher level of conflict with supervisor when compared to female respondents at work environment. This result aligns with findings of [61], but contradicts with [60], [62]. There is a positive correlation between gender and the conflict management with supervisor at work. From the analysis it's proved that there is a significant association between annual income and their response towards performance management followed by the company. This result aligns with findings of [64], but contradicts with [63]. From the analysis it's proved that there is a significant variance between age and their response

towards the appraisal system, succession planning and employee engagement. Respondents from 18-25 years were responded that more employee engagement initiatives were organized by the company and the succession planning programs organized by the company were more effective within the company. This result aligns with findings of [67]. From discriminant analysis the researchers found that there is a significant association between compensation that matches the skills and experience offered by the company with gender, age, annual income, educational qualification and years of experience. Out of many independent variable, education qualification acts as important independent variable with higher coefficient which predicts the compensation that matches the skills and experience offered by the company than the other independent variables. This result aligns with the findings of [65], [66] and [75].

IX. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

HR Managers acts as a business enabler in terms of formulating the policies and its strategies related to Induction, recruitment and selection process, performance management, Learning and development opportunities and career development initiatives offered within the company. The study helps in identifying and promoting various HRM practices such as employee engagement, succession planning initiative, performance management, compensation management, appraisal process, and conflict management etc. Reducing the conflict management among the workers by organizing various initiatives like open house sessions, engaging the employees through fun at workplace, counselling sessions and learning opportunities will result in creating the conflict free culture and a healthy work space within the company. This research helps in identifying the impact of demographic profile on strategic HRM practices and its challenges faced by HR managers in IT firm. This study can be extended to IT and other industries in India and abroad to get a fair understanding towards the impact on strategic HRM practices and its challenges faced by HR managers.

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